

**The Poet as the Coder:
the Conversation between Text and Code in the Techno-poetic Work of Fabrizio Venerandi
as a Practical/Theoretical Approach to DH and CCS**

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What happens when, in order to read the totality of a poetic digital text, we have to access and read the code that supports its functioning? How can we approach the parallel reading of both the poems and the code, and why is it important to do so? Should the digital author be able to master both literary writing and computer programming?

In the ebook *Poesie elettroniche* (“Electronic poems”, 2016), Fabrizio Venerandi has shaped the code in order to respond to his poetic intention, thus becoming the author of both the literary text and the programming code that makes it readable and accessible. More specifically, the use of code to hide verses that Venerandi “wouldn’t want to read again” and “wouldn’t want to freeze in a peculiar form” underscores the fact that computer code is not only intended for machines to interpret and execute, but also for humans to read and engage with.

Venerandi’s work can thus be used as an example of how to develop methods of analysis in DH and CCS, and as a way to build bridges between researchers in the Humanities and in Computer science: for the former, it becomes a way to get their hands on the code while working on the literary and critical analysis of the poetic text, for the latter, it becomes a way to get closer to the human and social aspects of the code they work with.

Starting from the hypothesis that the importance of “‘making things’ as a way of doing theoretical work” (Saum-Pascual 2020) is not only valid for electronic literature, through the parallel analysis of the two layers of the text written by Venerandi, this paper aims to propose methods and ways for interdisciplinary work between researchers from different fields.